

**THE METHODS USED TO TEACH THE LEXICAL-SEMANTIC
PROPERTIES OF PROVERBS INCLUDED IN PRIMARY SCHOOL NATIVE
LANGUAGE TEXTBOOKS.**

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Abstract. This article examines the lexical-semantic properties of various proverbs used in primary school textbooks and discusses how to teach them to primary school students through various modern technologies and methods. The proverb presents new and diverse methods that, when applied during the lesson, lead to positive results.

Keywords: lexical-semantic, gamification, problematic education, interactive approach, group method, results and skills.

Proverbs, which are the gems of national thought, play a significant role in educating and developing the student's personality. Not only does the proverb embellish the speaker's speech, but it also enriches their thinking and worldview, playing a crucial role in nurturing a mature individual. Until this period, a number of studies have been conducted on proverbs, which are beautiful examples of the folklore genre. It is known that primary education (grades 1-4) is considered the most fundamental stage of our education system. It is precisely during this period that the learner transitions from the play age, gradually developing into a mature individual by enhancing their knowledge. There are many methods for educating students. One of them is considered to be the oral creative heritage of the people. That is, various tales, legends, and proverbs hold great significance. The ideological content of folk proverbs includes encouraging honesty, promoting goodness, enriching one's spirituality,

helping to understand oneself, and, in general, the comprehensive education of the individual. Therefore, various colorful proverbs are used in school textbooks and literary works.

Folk proverbs have a significant place in the primary school 'Native Language and Reading Literacy' textbooks. Education serves as the primary tool in providing instruction and upbringing to students. In this context, it is essential for students to understand the main content derived from proverbs and to be able to apply them appropriately. Therefore, when teaching the lexical-semantic properties of proverbs to primary school students, special attention is paid to their age group and level of knowledge. Initially, proverbs that are easier to understand are taken from the 1st grade textbook 'Native Language and Reading Literacy'. In this case, in order to correctly analyze the proverb, attention must certainly be given to the semantic meanings of its lexical components. In order to use proverbs appropriately and apply them in their context, it is important to understand their lexical-semantic properties. Since proverbs are stable combinations, they express meaning in a holistic manner. Moreover, in expressing this holistic meaning, the components within proverbs also hold significant importance. In many genres of folk oral literature, including proverbs, various elements from nature (such as birds, animals, plants, their fruits, bodies, household items, tools, labor products, etc.) are skillfully used to reflect relationships, situations, and events in society in a simpler and clearer manner.

When teaching primary school students the lexical-semantic characteristics of proverbs, the following methods can be utilized:

In order for students to be able to analyze proverbs correctly and apply them appropriately to draw necessary conclusions, they must first understand the components of the proverb. It is important to consider that proverbs do not always convey their meaning in a straightforward manner. The components involved in proverbs should express semantic meaning according to the signs they represent in daily life. For example, if we analyze the components of the proverb 'the nightingale is good for the garden, the partridge for the mountain', the nightingale is a singing bird,

and the lexeme 'nightingale' is usually associated with terms like 'meadow', 'garden', and 'orchard'. The partridge is a wild bird that primarily lives in the mountains. Now, returning to the proverb, it is said that the nightingale is good for the garden. Thus, here the focus is not on the nightingale's singing qualities, but rather on its habitat. Similarly, the partridge being good for the mountains also emphasizes its living environment. Therefore, we can conclude from this proverb that 'Every living being has its own good place to live.' That is, we conclude from the proverb that people have a good place to live, their birthplace – their homeland.

When teaching this or similar proverbs to students, it is important to pay attention to their lexical-semantic composition and to draw general conclusions. Additionally, various didactic games can be used to teach proverbs to students based on their lexical-semantic characteristics. For example, various puzzles, tasks, and illustrated didactic games. The methodology for teaching lexical-semantic groups in the mother tongue to primary school students requires linking theoretical knowledge related to language with practical activities. Through this approach, students will learn to expand their vocabulary and understand the semantic connections between words. During lessons, using interactive methods to study lexical-semantic groups such as synonyms, antonyms, and polysemous words will be effective. Moreover, engaging students actively through games, problem-based learning, and group activities helps them to master their native language more deeply. Additionally, taking into account the age characteristics of students, it is recommended to explain topics through visual aids and everyday examples. This, in turn, helps them to feel the meanings of words more profoundly and to develop the skills to use them correctly in speech.

The main goal of teaching lexical-semantic groups to primary school students in their native language classes is to enhance vocabulary and teach students to understand the semantic relationships between words. Among such groups, synonyms, antonyms, polysemous words, and idiomatic expressions play an important role. The teaching methodology is based on interactive and visual methods appropriate to the age of the students.

Teaching methods and approaches:

1. **Interactive approach:** It is considered effective to encourage students to actively participate in learning lexical-semantic groups through games and role-playing activities. For example, tasks related to words are organized to discover synonyms.
2. **Group activity:** Students discover new words and discuss the connections between them by working in small groups. This method helps to conduct lessons in a lively and interesting manner.
3. **Visual aids:** Explaining the meanings of words through pictures, cards, or tables captures students' attention and engages them more deeply in the topic.
4. **Examples from daily life:** Teaching words in connection with real-life situations allows students to remember them and use them in everyday speech.

Results and skills:

By teaching lexical-semantic groups, students develop a nuanced understanding of word meanings and the skills to use them correctly in context. Moreover, they learn to express themselves more clearly in various speech situations. Teaching lexical-semantic groups in primary language classes is crucial for expanding children's vocabulary and preparing them for meaningful and accurate communication. Through the connections between such groups, students gain a deeper understanding of words and learn to use them correctly in speech.

Methodological approaches

1. **Working with synonyms and antonyms.** Teaching students to identify synonyms and antonyms enhances their vocabulary and ensures fluency in speech. For example, by practicing with alternative words, they become aware of the nuances of meaning.
2. **Polysemous words and contextual understanding.** By studying polysemous words that belong to lexical-semantic groups, children learn the various. They understand how it is used in contexts. Students perform exercises to determine the meaning of words based on context from texts and sentences.

3. **Games and interactive activities.** It is important to use games to make the process of learning lexical-semantic groups interesting in the classroom. For example, games like 'Find the Words' or 'Synonyms and Antonyms' allow lessons to be conducted actively and lively.

4. **Group activities and discussions.** Students learn new words by working in small groups and discuss the relationships between their meanings. This method develops their communicative skills and encourages independent thinking.

5. **Teaching with visual aids.** Using images and visual materials helps students better understand and remember the topic. With the help of pictures, children achieve faster word association and comprehension. In primary classes, new methods of teaching lexical-semantic words are of great importance in developing students' vocabulary. Here are some effective approaches:

Gamification. Making the learning process interesting using game elements. For example, enhancing knowledge through synonym and antonym quizzes, scoring and team games. Increase students' interest and encourage participation by using game elements in the course of the lesson. For example, collecting points or grades, running games and competitions in the classroom. This is especially useful when teaching synonyms and antonyms. Example: Card games - children find pairs of antonyms and collect points.

Interactive technologies: Teaching using electronic devices and educational applications. Students are helped to understand the meaning of words more deeply through special platforms or multimedia applications. Also, topics are explained more clearly through video and audio lessons. Benefit: Students learn better by seeing and hearing through multimedia.

Problem-based learning approach: Children are faced with word problem situations and work on them independently or in groups. This method involves students in independent thinking and research activities. Example: "Which word does not fit this sentence?" exercises with questions like

Contextual teaching: Explaining the meaning of words with real life situations of children. This method gives students the ability to use words in the right context. Example: Teaching the words "hot" and "cold" to associate with daily temperature.

Use of visual and audio materials: Explain the topic through pictures, charts, audios and videos. By seeing and hearing, students remember the subject more easily. Example: Teaching synonyms and antonyms with picture cards. All these methods are aimed at making the learning process interesting and effective, and help students develop solid vocabulary and skills.

To sum up, teaching proverbs in primary grades in the lexical-semantic method based on modern technologies and approaches introduced into our new education system is considered an effective method and greatly contributes to the improvement of the quality of education. Proverbs, which are the pride of our folklore, are a rare and invaluable educational tool that has been passed down from generation to generation for centuries.

References:

1. Abdusaidov B.H. Omitonim komponentli maqollarning leksik-semantik xususiyatlari haqida. "Fan,ta'lim va amaliyoti integratsiyasi" ilmiy-metodik jurnali, 2023, 59-62-b.
2. O'zbek xalq maqollari. – T:, 2005.
3. Ona tili va o'qish savodxonligi 1-qism [Matn]: 1-sinf uchun darslik/ I.Azimova [va boshq.]. – Toshkent Respublika ta'lim markazi, 2021. – 104 b
4. Pinxasov Y. O'zbek tili frazeologiyasi haqida. – Toshkent Fan, 1957
5. Sobirov A. O'zbek tilining leksik sathini sistemalar sistemasi sifatida tadqiq etish. – T:. Ma'naviyat, 2004. 92 – b
6. www.ziyo.uz
7. www.wikipedia.uz